

Biosorption of chromium(vi) by some algae

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Abstract : In the present study, biosorption of chromium(vi) from aqueous solutions was studied on two algae species *Synechococcus* sp. and *Asterocapsa* sp. in living condition with variation in initial metal concentration. The algae species were cultured in BG 11 medium, which was supplemented with 1–4 mg L⁻¹ of chromium(vi), and were harvested after 15 days of incubation. The total chlorophyll content and percent removal was determined. The maximum removal was 36% for *Synechococcus* sp. and 37.5% for *Asterocapsa* sp. The results suggest that both species could be used as bioadsorbent for removal of metal. The results also suggested that in living conditions, *Synechococcus* was found more suitable for removal of chromium(vi) from aqueous solution.

Keywords : Biosorption, algae, chromium(vi), total chlorophyll content, metal removal.

Introduction

Biotechnology has been investigated as an alternative method for treating the metal containing wastewater of low concentrations. Biosorption can be defined as the removal of metal or metalloids species, compound and particulates from solution using biological material¹. Large quantities of metal can be accumulated by a variety of process dependent and independent on metabolism. Living and dead biomass as well as cellular products such as polysaccharides can be used for metal removal. The biosorption technique provide effective method for metal removal which can be compared with techniques like ion exchange and is cost effective. Further it can play an important role to improve a zero waste economic policy especially in the case of biomass resulting from food, pharmaceuticals and wastewater treatments. Metal ions uptake by biosorption may involve the contribution of diffusion, adsorption, chelation, complexation and coordination or micro-precipitation mechanisms, depending on the specific biomass^{2,3}. The researches showed that algae may be more effective biosorbents than the other kinds of organisms. Blue-green algae, also called *Cyanobacteria*, including *Spirulina*, *Anabaena*, *Nostoc* and *Synechococcus* were the typical examples that showed

potential as biosorbents for efficient removal of heavy metals including cadmium from wastewaters⁴⁻⁶. Volesky and Holan have presented an exhaustive list of microbes and their metal-binding capacities⁷.

The aim of this study is to examine the possibility of using live *Synechococcus* sp. and *Asterocapsa* sp. to biologically remove chromium(vi) at low concentrations from wastewater. The toxicity and biosorption of chromium(vi) by live *Synechococcus* sp. and *Asterocapsa* sp. were investigated. Both factors are very important in developing *Synechococcus* sp. and *Asterocapsa* sp. for the treatment of wastewater containing heavy metals.

Results and discussion

Toxicity of chromium on total chlorophyll content of algae :

To investigate chromium(iv) tolerance, the living cells of *Synechococcus* sp. and *Asterocapsa* sp. were cultivated in solution containing chromium(vi) ions at various concentrations. The effects of chromium(vi) on total chlorophyll content of *Synechococcus* sp. and *Asterocapsa* sp., at different concentrations are shown in Fig. 1. The results indicated that there is a significant decrease in total chlorophyll content of *Asterocapsa* sp. when the

Fig. 1. Effect of chromium(vi) concentration on total chlorophyll content of *Synechococcus* sp. and *Asterocapsa* sp.

metal concentration was increased. The lowest total chlorophyll content was found in exposed alga is 0.0738 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of chromium(vi) on day 15. There is no decrease in total chlorophyll content of *Synechococcus* sp. The figure also shows that *Synechococcus* sp. has a good tolerance for chromium(vi) metal. The highest chlorophyll content found in exposed alga was 13.8714 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ with respect to 4 mg L^{-1} of chromium(vi) on day 15.

Effect of initial metal concentration on biosorption :

The initial chromium(vi) concentration remarkably influenced the metal adsorption rate at equilibrium stage. It was found that percent biosorption of chromium(vi) for *Asterocapsa* sp. was increased up on increasing the concentration. But in case of *Synechococcus* sp. percent biosorption of chromium(vi) was increased on increasing concentration. The maximum removal is 37.5% and 36% for *Synechococcus* sp. and *Asterocapsa* sp. respectively.

Requirements for developing a practical bioremoval process for heavy metals include low-cost production of plant biomass, ease of removing the biomass from suspension, high maximum specific adsorption and the capability to reduce metal concentration to very low residual levels. The *Synechococcus* sp. and *Asterocapsa* sp. are very easy to harvest and are potentially produced in mass culture.

Experimental

Biosorbent material :

Synechococcus sp. and *Asterocapsa* sp. were collected from natural pond and grown in BG 11 medium⁸ in the Phycology Lab of the Botany Department, University of Allahabad under controlled condition is maintained in growth chamber, lighted by both fluorescence and indescendent source 94 K Lux light, 14 : 10 LD, temperature 30 ± 2 °C. Two week old *Synechococcus* sp. and *Asterocapsa* sp. were used in the experiments.

Biosorption experiments :

The chromium solution was prepared by diluting standard chromium solution to the desired concentrations. The freshly diluted solutions were used for each biosorption study. The BG 11 medium was supplemented with four nominal concentrations (1, 2, 3 and 4 mg L^{-1}) of chromium prepared from $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ (Qualigens). The final pH of solutions were adjusted to 7.5. Fresh weight of algae i.e. 0.02 g was inoculated into each flask containing various concentrations of chromium. Algae cultured in the nutrient medium without heavy metal served as control. All the experiments were performed in triplicate.

The residual concentration of chromium(vi) was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (ECIL-4141, Hyderabad).

Note

The percent removal of chromium(vi) by algae was calculated by using the eq. (1),

$$\% R = \frac{C_i - C_e}{C_i} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where, R is removal, C_i and C_e are initial and final equilibrium concentrations of metal ion in solution respectively.

Total chlorophyll content :

The total chlorophyll content was determined by absorption spectra of algal extracts in methanol by spectrophotometer. The absorbance of the extract was measured at 665 nm. The total chlorophyll content was calculated by eq. (2),

$$\text{Total chlorophyll content } (\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}) = \text{O. D.} \times 13.42 \quad (2)$$

where, O.D. is optical density

Conclusions :

This study leads to the conclusion that adsorption process of only *Asterocapsa* sp. were apparently affected by initial metal concentration, *Synechococcus* sp. has a

good tolerance to increased concentration of chromium(vi). The results suggest that both the selected species could be used as a bioadsorbent for removal of metal ions from aqueous solutions, but *Synechococcus* sp. has a good potential for biosorption of chromium(vi) metal. The experimental data presented here indicated that these algae have promising metal adsorbing characteristics. The process is more cost-efficient than other conventional techniques in treatment of large volume of wastewater with low concentrations of pollutants.

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